

Infrared Spectra of Iron(II) Complexes with N,N-Dimethylformamide and N,N-Dimethylthioformamide*

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Infrared spectra and assignment for the vibration frequencies are given for $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Br}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_3$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_2\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_2\text{Br}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_2\text{I}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_3$, and compared with the spectra of the free DMF and DMTF. The results are found to be in agreement with the bond length variation rules.

A MIDES are coordinated to Lewis acids through the "hard" oxygen atoms of the C=O group whereas thioamides coordinate through the "soft" sulfur atoms of the C=S group. In order to compare the changes in bond lengths involved in coordination by both types of ligands the IR spectra of the following adducts of N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) and N,N-dimethylthioformamide (DMTF) have been studied: $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Br}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_3$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_2\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_2\text{Br}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_2\text{I}_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_3$. In the ClO_4^- complexes the metal ions are in octahedrally coordinated by DMF and DMTF molecules, 1 respectively and the anions are in outer sphere positions. On the other hand, in tetrahedral halide complexes the halide ligands are coordinated in the inner sphere of the central iron(II) ion^{1,2}.

Experimental

The preparation of the complexes has been described previously¹. The infrared spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 180 IR spectrometer. KBr pellets were used to measure the infrared spectra in the range from 4000 to 300 cm^{-1} , whereas Nujol mulls were used to obtain the spectra from 525 to 32 cm^{-1} . The preparation of the pellets and the nujol mulls were performed with freshly prepared complexes in a dry box filled with dry nitrogen gas¹. The infrared spectra were also recorded under dry nitrogen atmosphere to prevent slow decomposition of the substances in contact with air-oxygen and air-water^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

IR spectra and assignments for DMF and DMTF as given by Durgaprasad³ and other

TABLE I—INFRARED ABSORPTION BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF DMF AND THE IRON(II)-DMF COMPLEXES WITH THE ASSIGNMENT OF THE SIGNIFICANT VIBRATIONS

DMF (Lit. ³)	DMF	$\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_3$	$\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Cl}_2$	$\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Br}_2$	Vibration*
		645 s			ClO_4^-
660 s	655 s	685 s	680 s	685 s	$\nu(\text{O}-\text{N})$
870 m	865 m	855 m	851 s	865 s	$\nu_\sigma(\text{C}'\text{N})$
		860 m			ClO_4^-
	940 m				ClO_4^-
1067 m	1067 m		1053 m	1060 m	$\nu(\text{CH}_2)$
1099 vs	1090 s		1110 s	1113 s	$\nu(\text{CH}_2)$
	1150 **	1145 v			ClO_4^-
		1160 s			$\nu(\text{CH}_2)$ -
		1170 s			$\nu(\text{CH}_2)$ -
1268 s	1255 s	1250 m	1245 m	1250 m	$\nu_\alpha(\text{C}'\text{N})$
1395 vs	1 85 s	1370 s	1372 s,	1380 s	$\delta_\sigma(\text{CH}_2)$, $\nu(\text{CN})$
1410 s	1405 m	1415 m	1415 m	1405 v	$\delta(\text{CH})$
1410 **				1180 s	$\delta_\sigma(\text{CH}_2)$
1450 m	1440 s	1455 v	1430 s	1435 m	$\delta_\alpha(\text{CH}_2)$
1512 m	1500 m	1490 m	1492 m	1500 m	$\nu_\alpha(\text{CH}_2)$, $\delta_\alpha(\text{CH}_2)$, $\nu(\text{CN})$
1685 s	1675 s	1640 s	1640 s	1650 s	$\nu(\text{CO})$, $\nu(\text{CN})$
		1650 s	1650 s		
		1655 s	1655 s		

vs, s, m, w means very strong, strong, medium, weak, respectively.

* ν , δ , ν , α and σ mean stretching, bending, rocking, asymmetric, and symmetric, respectively.

** not resolved.

* Dedicated to Professor A. K. Dey on the occasion of his 60th birthday.

TABLE 2—INFRARED ABSORPTION BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF DMTF AND THE IRON(II)-DMTF COMPLEXES WITH THE ASSIGNMENT OF THE SIGNIFICANT VIBRATIONS

DMTF(Lit.*)	DMTF	$\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	$\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_5\text{Cl}$	$\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_4\text{Br}_2$	$\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_3\text{I}_3$	Vibration*
		625 s				ClO_4^-
		635 s				ClO_4^-
		680 w	680 w		680 w	
828/s	820 m	820 m	825 m	825 m	815 w	$\nu_{\text{C}'\text{N}}$
		850 m				ClO_4^-
970 s	970 s	968 m	948 s	935 s	940 m	$\nu(\text{CS})$
1058 s	1050 s	1057 m	1050 w	1059 m	1059 m	$r(\text{CH}_2)$
		1110 s	1113 m		1110 m	$r(\text{CH}_2)$
1140 s	1128 s	1175 m	1136 s	1135 s		$r(\text{CH}_2)$
	1205 s	1200 m	1197 w	1195 w		$\nu_{\text{C}'\text{N}}$
		1250 w	1246 w	1240 w		
			1374 s	1378 m	1240 s	
1405 m	1400 s	1405 s	1406 s	1408 m	1353	
1410 sh	1410 **		1415 s		1370 m	$\delta(\text{CH})$
1420 vs	1420 **	1440 m	1432 m	1432 m	1420 s	$\delta_{\text{C}'\text{H}}$
1450 s	1460 s	1460 m	1462 m	1462 m	1420 m	$\delta_{\text{C}'\text{H}}$
1472 s	1472 **		1492 m			$\delta_{\text{C}'\text{H}}$
1560 s	1545 s	1570 s	1568 s	1570 s	1553 m	$\nu(\text{CN})$

*, ** see table 1

 TABLE 3—INFRARED ABSORPTION BANDS IN THE REGION FROM 525 TO 32 cm^{-1}

Compound	Absorption frequency cm^{-1}										
DMF	403			353	318	255					
$\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	415	397	384			239	220			142	
$\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_5\text{Cl}$	414		380	353	315	290	216			142	
$\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_4\text{Br}_2$	413		386	360	320	280	220	190	163	143	104
DMTF					274	215					
$\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_2$	519	403			308		174	140	130	100	
$\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_5\text{Cl}$	516	407	393								
$\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_4\text{Br}_2$	505	403	343	325	295	215	190		136	117	
$\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_3\text{I}_3$	512	405		328	270	214				90	
$\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_2\text{I}_4$	515	405	390	330	266			146			

authors⁴⁻⁸ were confirmed. The data for the iron(II) complexes are given in Tables 1 and 2. The first bond length variation rule predicts⁹ a lengthening of the bonds directly adjacent to the donor-acceptor interaction. In the complexes under study, these are the O=C and S=C bond in DMF and DMTF, respectively. The absorption line for DMTF at 970 cm^{-1} , assigned as S-C stretching vibration, is strongly lowered in the tetrahedral halide complexes and to a lesser extent in the octahedral perchlorate complex. The lowering of the O-C stretching frequencies of DMF at 1675 cm^{-1} is well pronounced both in the halide and the perchlorate complexes.

The comparison of the results obtained for the perchlorate complexes reveals that changes in the C=S bond lengths are smaller than in the C=O bond lengths, although the Fe-S bond appears stronger than the Fe-O bond. As back donation seems involved in the Fe-S bond, the S-C bond should be lengthened to a lesser extent than the C-O bond. This also means that differences in the outer sphere interactions with the ClO_4^- groups should exist. The changes in charge redistribution due to complex formation seem more strongly spread over the whole system in the DMTF complexes.

The second bond length variation rule⁹ predicts a shortening of the C-N bond and a lengthening of the N-C' bonds. In DMTF, the N-C' stretching vibration at 1545 cm^{-1} is seen to be increased and hence the C-N bond shortened. In DMF, the N-C' stretching vibrations are highly coupled so that the shifts due to complex formation could not be detected. Both, the symmetric as well as the asymmetric N-C' stretching frequencies are found to be lowered by complex formation with DMF and DMTF complexes, respectively.

In agreement with the second rule a shortening of the C-H bond length was found, as can be seen from the comparison of the C-H stretching frequencies at 1405 cm^{-1} in DMF and at 1400 cm^{-1} in DMTF and the corresponding absorption lines of the complexes.

The bond length variation concept leads to the suggestion of a terminating group effect: changes in charge distribution due to a donor-acceptor interaction should be smaller with increasing distance from the site of the interaction but again more developed at the end groups of the complex⁹. The frequencies of the rocking vibrations at the (CH_2) groups in DMF and DMTF show indeed stronger changes than the frequencies of the C-H deformation frequencies.

The frequencies of the far-infrared absorption lines in the region of 525 to 32 cm^{-1} are presented in Table 3.

The Fe-halide stretching frequencies lie at 325, 315 and 270 cm^{-1} for $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_2\text{Cl}_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and the two bromide compounds, respectively. It can be seen, that the coordination of the Fe-central ion to the soft S-atom in DMTF leads to a weaker Fe-Cl bond than the coordination to the hard O-atom in DMF. Comparison of the ratio of the Fe-Br and the Fe-Cl frequencies with the square root of the atomic masses of Cl and Br show that the Fe-Br bond is by a factor of about 1.5 stronger than the Fe-Cl bond. Any differences between $\text{Fe}(\text{DMTF})_2\text{Br}_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Br}_2$ could not be resolved at the said line at 270 cm^{-1} . The Fe-I stretching vibrations should be found at frequencies between 212 and 207 cm^{-1} . Because of the very weak Fe-I bond in these complexes (decomposition of Fe-I complexes takes place readily⁹) the line at 146 cm^{-1} should be assigned to this vibration. The Fe-S stretching vibrations are found between 343 and 393 cm^{-1} , whereby the highest values are found for the perchlorate- and the iodo-complex. In DMTF, these vibrations vary to a greater extent than the corresponding Fe-O vibrations found between 384 and 386 cm^{-1} ¹⁰⁻¹². The absorption lines at 220, 216 and 220 cm^{-1} are assigned to the O-Fe-O deformation frequencies of $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_2\text{Br}_2$ ¹².

The lowering of the line at 519 cm^{-1} at the DMTF complexes has been assigned to the lowering of the C-S stretching vibration (see Table 2) and not by the S-C deformation vibration which is

involved in this complex coupled vibration. This may be deduced because the line at 215 cm^{-1} which is considered as the S-C-N deformation vibration is not significantly shifted. The line at 403 cm^{-1} in both DMF and DMTF is assigned to the C'-N-C' deformation frequency.

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